

COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE

**Summary of the selected good practices
of countering hate speech online
in Slovenia, Croatia and Serbia**

Project “BEHAVE – SEE Beyond Hate: Learning and Acting to Counter Hate Speech Online in South East Europe”

Project coordinators: Peace Institute, Ljubljana

Partners: University of Ljubljana (Faculty of Social Sciences),

Centre for Peace Studies, Zagreb, Novi Sad School of Journalism, Novi Sad

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FOREWORD

The spreading of hate speech online is making it increasingly difficult to secure human rights, to protect human dignity, and to maintain the democratic standards of public communication and debate.

This troubling form of public communication calls not only for the legal system and media regulators to react to instances of illegal hate speech. It reveals the need for engagement and responsiveness on the part of other institutions and sectors – political institutions and actors, media and communications platforms, civil society, educational and research institutions, and not least individual citizens.

The organizations partnered under the project “BEHAVE – SEE Beyond Hate: Learning and Acting to Counter Hate Speech Online in South East Europe” focused the initial study on the practices and actors battling hate speech in the target countries – Croatia, Slovenia, and Serbia. First, we summarized the definitions of hate speech used in the three countries and reviewed the available analyses of (online) hate speech. We identified the important actors countering (online) hate speech in these countries and collected a wide array of related good practices. We concluded our research by carefully studying and describing the few anti-hate speech practices that stand out due to their extent, range, creativity, complexity and duration.

Apart from practices from Croatia, Slovenia and Serbia, we studied and summarized a few examples of online hate speech curbing measures from other European countries and at the cross-national, European level.

Our research was conducted between April and June 2020.

Our review of good practices aims primarily to advance the exchange of knowledge and experience between relevant institutions and organizations in the three target countries. The publication of the review of good practices will be followed by a regional conference. In addition, the purpose of the publication is to make experts and the broader public aware of the spreading of hate speech online and to encourage them to act.

In seeking to share knowledge and research, to act against online hate speech, and to develop educational programmes, the “BEHAVE ” project links four partner organizations: two from Slovenia – the Peace Institute in a coordinating role and the University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Social Sciences, with its ‘Spletno oko’ hotline, one from Croatia – the Centre for Peace Studies in Zagreb—, and one from Serbia – the Novi Sad School of Journalism.

The project is financed by the EU’s Justice, and Rights, Equality and Citizenship programme.

This publication presents a summary of the good practices that were given a detailed presentation in a publication in the languages of the target countries.

CONTENTS

1	OVERVIEW OF GOOD PRACTICES OF COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE IN SLOVENIA, CROATIA AND SERBIA	3
	SLOVENIA	4
	CROATIA	9
	SERBIA	11
	SUMMARY OF THE SELECTED GOOD PRACTICES OF COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE IN SLOVENIA, CROATIA AND SERBIA	15
2	SLOVENIA	16
	Spletno oko hotline	16
	Anti-Hate Speech Council	17
	Workshops for high schools “Solidarity-Equality-Sameness”	18
	Ombudsman for the rights of RTV Slovenija viewers, listeners, readers, and programme content users	19
	Judgment of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia in the case of hate speech against Roma in a comment on the website of Radio Krka ..	20
	Public debate following the establishment of the Zlovenija portal	21
3	CROATIA	22
	Dosta je mržnje reporting tool	22
	Web portal Medijska pismenost (Media Literacy)	23
	Mobile application by the Ministry of the Interior – Security and Trust	24
4	SERBIA	25
	The “Virtual becomes reality” initiative	25
	“Anonymous Hatred” and “H8index Database of Verbal Violence”	26
	Deconstruction of Fake News (Fake News Tragač)	27
	Campaign against hate speech on YouTube – “Clickbait” and “Drama” videos	28

OVERVIEW OF GOOD PRACTICES OF COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE IN SLOVENIA, CROATIA AND SERBIA

SLOVENIA

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Spletno oko hotline

SECTOR

IT, self-regulation of online media portals, social networks

PERIOD

2006—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana

INFORMATION

<https://www.spletno-ok.si/>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Anti-Hate Speech Council

SECTOR

civil society

PERIOD

1. 9. 2014—29. 2. 2016

ORGANIZERS

Peace Institute, in cooperation with the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana, the Human Rights Ombudsman, and the Multimedia Centre of RTV Slovenia

INFORMATION

<https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/projects/responding-hatespeech-activation-independent-conjunctive-body-act/>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Workshops for high schools “Solidarity-Equality-Sameness”

SECTOR

education

PERIOD

1. 1. 2020—30. 11. 2020

ORGANIZERS

Peace Institute

INFORMATION

<https://www.mirovni-institut.si/projekti/solidarnost-enakost-istost-2/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **Ombudsman for the rights of RTV Slovenia viewers, listeners, readers, and programme content users**

SECTOR media, self-regulation

PERIOD 2008—ongoing

ORGANIZERS RTV Slovenia

INFORMATION <https://www.rtv slo.si/varuh/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **Judgment of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia in the case of hate speech against Roma in a comment on the website of Radio Krka**

SECTOR legal sector

PERIOD 2019

ORGANIZERS the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia

INFORMATION [text of the judgment](#)

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **Public debate following the establishment of the Zlovenija portal**

SECTOR civil society, social networks

PERIOD October, 2015

ORGANIZERS unknown

INFORMATION <https://zlovenija.tumblr.com/tagged/pisma>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **Dekontamination of hate speech**

SECTOR civil society: recording cases of hate speech, counter-narration workshops

PERIOD 2013—ongoing

ORGANIZERS Pride Parade Association

INFORMATION <http://www.dekontraminacija.org/>
<http://www.ljubljana.pride.org/event/dekontraminacija-sovrazni-govor-na-spletu/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **NiPrav.si (web portal with recommendations for acting in cases of hate speech)**

SECTOR civil society

PERIOD 2019—ongoing

ORGANIZERS Legebitra

INFORMATION <https://nprav.si/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE **Project Sovraštvo.si, Campaign Against Hatred**

SECTOR civil society

PERIOD 2018—ongoing

ORGANIZERS Institute Državljan D (Citizen D)

INFORMATION <http://www.sovrastvo.si/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE | **Overcoming the culture of hate (Ljubljana Pride festival 2019)**

SECTOR | civil society: workshops, conferences on hate speech

PERIOD | 2019

ORGANIZERS | Pride Parade Association

INFORMATION | <http://ljubljanapride.org/2019/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE | **Campaign and movement “No Hate Speech” (We CAN! Handbook)**

SECTOR | civil society

PERIOD | 2013—2017

ORGANIZERS | for Slovenia: Office of the Republic of Slovenia for Youth

INFORMATION | <https://www.gov.si/zbirke/projekti-in-programi/kampanja-ne-sovraznemu-govoru/>
<https://mlad.si/e-katalogi/Zmoremo!/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE | **Blog “In media res”**

SECTOR | civil society

PERIOD | 2018—ongoing

ORGANIZERS | Boris Vezjak, university professor

INFORMATION | <https://vezjak.com/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE | **Events with the aim of reducing stereotypes (living libraries, workshops, round tables)**

SECTOR | civil society, education

PERIOD | different

ORGANIZERS | for example: Maribor Youth Cultural Centre (Don’t hate, listen!), Dravinja Valley Youth Centre (Young Ambassadors of Intercultural Dialogue, Start the Change)

INFORMATION | <http://www.maribor.si/dokument.aspx?id=31995>
<https://www.mamd.si/projekt/>
<https://www.mccd.si/svet-obarvali-z-razlicnostjo/#more-5656>

CROATIA

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Dosta je mržnje reporting tool

SECTOR

civil society, self-regulation of social networks, monitoring hate speech, education

PERIOD

2016—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Human Rights House Zagreb and Centre for Peace Studies

INFORMATION

www.dostajemrznje.hr

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Web portal Medijska pismenost (Media Literacy)

SECTOR

media literacy, education

PERIOD

2018—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Agency for Electronic Media

INFORMATION

<https://www.medijskapismenost.hr/>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Mobile application by the Ministry of the Interior – Security and Trust

SECTOR

law enforcement, active citizenship

PERIOD

2015—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Ministry of the Interior

INFORMATION

<https://policija.gov.hr/aplikacije-za-e-dojave-sumnjivih-dogadjaja/172>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Arterarij: Hide somewhere far away. To death.

SECTOR

culture and art (theatre)

PERIOD

2019—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

non-governmental organization Arterarij

INFORMATION

<https://arterarij.webnode.hr/portfolio/>
<https://www.novolist.hr/ostalo/kultura/kazaliste/teatar-savjesti-i-rastvaranja-mrznje-kriticarka-govedic-o-dvije-nove-predstave/>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Pink megaphone

SECTOR

civil society: reporting violence, threats and hate speech

PERIOD

2011—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Zagreb Pride

INFORMATION

<https://rozimegafon.org/>

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

Safer Internet Centre

SECTOR

civil society, self-regulation of social networks

PERIOD

2016—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Safer Internet Centre

INFORMATION

<https://csi.hr/hotline/>

SERBIA

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

The “Virtual becomes reality” initiative

SECTOR

civil society: human rights, education, advocacy

PERIOD

2012—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

youth organization Libero, Belgrade

INFORMATION

<http://virtuelnpostajestvarnost.org/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

“Anonymous Hatred” and “H8index Database of Verbal Violence”

SECTOR

civil society: education, reporting on the human rights situation

PERIOD

2017—2018

ORGANIZERS

Belgrade Centre for Human Rights in cooperation with the New Media Centre LIBER

INFORMATION

<http://www.bgcentar.org.rs/anonimna-mrznja-prijavi-govor-mrznje-na-internetu/>
<https://bit.ly/2OFgCgr>
<http://www.h8index.org/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Deconstruction of Fake News (Fake News Tragač)

SECTOR

civil society: facts checking, public awareness

PERIOD

2017—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Novi Sad School of Journalism

INFORMATION

<https://fakenews.rs/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Campaign against hate speech on YouTube – “Clickbait” and “Drama” videos

SECTOR

civil society: awareness raising, self-regulation of social networks, advocacy, education

PERIOD

2017—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Deutsche Welle Academy

INFORMATION

<https://www.dw.com/en/dw-akademie-in-serbia-and-the-western-balkans/a-18497351>
<https://www.dw.com/sr/klikovi-ali-i-odgovornost/a-48346807>
 The campaign videos:
[Clickbait \(Klikbejt\)](#)
[Drama](#)

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

BlogOpen

SECTOR

civil society: self-regulation, advocacy

PERIOD

2007—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

New Media Centre LIBER

INFORMATION

<https://blogopen.rs/>

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

A collection of hate speech cases

SECTOR

civil society: awareness raising, education, advocacy

PERIOD

2013

ORGANIZERS

Media Centre Belgrade

INFORMATION

[A collection of hate speech cases.pdf](#)

TITLE OF THE
GOOD PRACTICE

TV series “In the web”

SECTOR

civil society: awareness raising, education, advocacy

PERIOD

2017—ongoing

ORGANIZERS

Share foundation

INFORMATION

<https://www.umrezi.rs/>

SUMMARY OF THE SELECTED GOOD PRACTICES OF COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE IN SLOVENIA, CROATIA AND SERBIA

SLOVENIA

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Spletno oko hotline

- **WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?**

Spletno oko works as a hotline, enabling the anonymous reporting of hate speech and child sexual abuse images online, processing them and cooperating with the Police and the Prosecutor's Office regarding potentially illegal content. Regarding hate speech, it is active on several international projects, publishes various publications, and regularly organizes events and other activities with the goal of raising public awareness and to connect experts in developing good practices.

Besides the hotline, particularly successful activities of Spletno oko aimed at combating hate speech online were the partnership within the projects of monitoring the responsiveness of social networks to hate speech reports in cooperation with the European Commission, and signing of the Code of Hate Speech Regulation on web portals with some of the leading news portals in Slovenia in 2010.

- **PERIOD**

Spletno oko was established in September 2006, and is still active today.

- **ORGANIZERS**

The Spletno oko hotline is part of the Safer Internet Centre, coordinated by the Faculty of Social Sciences of the University of Ljubljana, in cooperation with partners Arnes, the Slovenian Association of Friends of Youth and the Youth Information and Counselling Centre of Slovenia. It also cooperates with the Office of the State Prosecutor General, General Police Directorate, and representatives of the media.

- **FINANCING**

The Safer Internet Centre project is funded by the INEA at the European Commission (through the Connecting Europe Facility) and by the Slovenian Ministry of Public Administration.

- **INFORMATION / CONTACT**

Information: <https://www.spletno-oko.si/>

Contact: info@spletno-oko.si (for hate speech: Urša Valentič)

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Anti-Hate Speech Council

● WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The Anti-Hate Speech Council (renamed 'the Anti-Discriminatory and Hate Speech Council' in its second term; hereafter 'the Council') was an informal, independent body that, during its two terms (2015/2016 and 2016/2017), responded to instances of hate speech in Slovenia by issuing public written statements on the basis of written initiatives by legal or natural persons, and suggestions of Council members. The Council used the Council of Europe's definition which labels as hate speech "all forms of expression which spread, incite, promote or justify racial hatred, xenophobia, anti-Semitism or other forms of hatred based on intolerance, including: intolerance expressed by aggressive nationalism and ethnocentrism, discrimination and hostility against minorities, migrants and people of immigrant origin." Additionally, it followed clauses from the Constitution of the Republic of Slovenia, and from laws on the equal treatment and prohibition of public expressions of hatred, violence and intolerance.

Through public engagement, the Council aimed to contribute to solving the problem of hate speech in Slovenia, to help establish the standards of public discourse, to foster public debate, and to raise public awareness. It sought to connect representatives of the governmental and non-governmental sectors, experts and other interested publics in a joint body that advocated for a zero-tolerance attitude to hate speech through action and systematic responsiveness.

● PERIOD

September 2014 – February 2016

● ORGANIZERS

The Peace Institute, cooperating with the University of Ljubljana's Faculty of Social Sciences (its 'Spletno oko' hotline for reporting online hate speech and images of sexual child abuse), the Human Rights Ombudsman, and the Multimedia Centre of RTV Slovenija.

● FINANCING

EGP Financial Mechanism, and the Norwegian Financial Mechanism, 2009–2014.

● INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/govor/>

Project presentation in English: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/en/projects/responding-hate-speech-activation-independent-conjunctive-body-act/>

Contact: Veronika Bajt, project head: veronika.bajt@mirovni-institut.si

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Workshops for high schools "Solidarity-Equality-Sameness"

● WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The main objective of the practice is to inform students on a multifaceted basis about migration with the goal to break stereotypes, fear and hatred, and empower them to act responsibly towards the migration issue by promoting the concepts of solidarity (pragmatic-daily level), equality (political-ideological level) and sameness (humanistic-universalist level) both within school classes, the local environment and the wider society. The key activities include the preparation, implementation and evaluation of workshops in secondary schools throughout Slovenia, as well as the preparation of learning scenarios that emerge from the needs and wishes of schools. Target groups are: high-school students, high-school teachers and professors, migrants, refugees, asylum seekers and the general public.

● PERIOD

2015–2019

● ORGANIZERS

The practice has been implemented by the Peace Institute, and non-government, research and civil society organizations, striving through scientific-research work and public actions for an open community capable of critical thinking and based on the principles of equality, accountability, solidarity, human rights and the rule of law. It is the advocate of vulnerable groups and in cooperation with them, strives to eliminate discrimination.

● FINANCING

The practice has been financed by the government office for communication (up to €8,000 per year). With the new government, the funds already allocated for this year are under question.

● INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <https://www.mirovni-institut.si/projekti/solidarnost-enakost-istost-2/>

Contact: Lana Zdravkovič, lana.zdravkovic@mirovni-institut.si

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Ombudsman for the rights of RTV Slovenija viewers, listeners, readers, and programme content users

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The ombudsman for the rights of RTV Slovenija viewers, listeners, readers, and programme content users (hereafter 'the ombudsman') is a mechanism of self-regulation which helps decrease and remove hate speech online. The institution, established by Slovenia's public broadcaster, enables citizens to object to questionable practices, e.g. by filing complaints about hate speech in programming and on MMC, the broadcaster's web portal which ranks among the most visited news websites in the country. Also, the institution can be seen as an attempt to ally a media outlet with its audience.

The ombudsman processes opinions, complaints, remark, and suggestions of RTV Slovenija content users, mediating between them and the content creators. By addressing audience responses, it strengthens dialogue between the two sides, and balances user rights against the authorial independence of RTV Slovenija content creators.

• PERIOD

2008–ongoing

• ORGANIZERS

RTV Slovenija

• FINANCING

RTV Slovenija

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <https://www.rtvlo.si/varuh/>

Contact: Ilinka Todorovski, the ombudsman for the rights of RTV Slovenija's viewers, listeners, readers, and programme content users, varuh@rtvlo.si

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Judgment of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia in the case of hate speech against Roma in a comment on the website of Radio Krka

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

In 2019, the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia decided on the case against the accused for the criminal offence of public incitement to hatred, violence or intolerance under Article 297 of the Criminal Code for hateful online comment. It confirmed the conviction of the District Court in Novo mesto, which found the defendant guilty in 2013. The decision differs significantly from previous hate speech jurisprudence, which followed much stricter, almost unrealistic criteria for conviction. The message delivered by this decision is of wider significance. With its extensive argumentation about the decision, it represents an important dividing line in the judicial treatment of hate speech. It sets an example for further judgments, as well as guidance to prosecutors regarding decisions to prosecute potentially illegal hate speech, particularly online.

• PERIOD

The judgment was decided on 4 July 2019.

• ORGANIZERS

The case was adjudicated by the Supreme Court of the Republic of Slovenia on the basis of a request for protection of legality against the judgment of the High Court in Ljubljana by the Supreme State Prosecutor. The arguments he cites summarize numerous efforts by experts to a more appropriate interpretation of Article 297.

• FINANCING

As a state institution, the Supreme Court and the Supreme Prosecutor's Office are financed from the budget of the Republic of Slovenia.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information:

Text of the judgment: [http://www.sodnapraksa.si/?q=65803&database\[SOVS\]=SOVS&submit=i%C5%A1%C4%8Di&rowsPerPage=20&page=0&id=2015081111431656](http://www.sodnapraksa.si/?q=65803&database[SOVS]=SOVS&submit=i%C5%A1%C4%8Di&rowsPerPage=20&page=0&id=2015081111431656)

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Public debate following the establishment of the Zlovenija portal

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The Zlovenija portal was established via the Tumblr platform as an answer to numerous extreme cases of hate speech against refugees on social networks, to which the authorities did not respond. Informally organized individuals exposed the most radical cases and their authors publicly in order to “set a mirror” and, as a “pillar of shame”, warn about the inappropriateness of publicly stated hatred. The primary targets of their message were, therefore, the authors of extreme hate speech, but also the general public in terms of opening a debate on the topic of tolerating and responding to hate speech online. The initiative also addressed the leading responsible institutions, which, according to the organizers, gave the impression with their passivity that the human rights protection mechanisms in the country had failed, giving legitimacy to self-initiated, albeit extreme forms of response from civil society.

• PERIOD

The portal was active from October until November 2015; however, the ensuing public debate continued for some time thereafter.

• ORGANIZERS

The website was set up by anonymous and informally organized individuals (or one individual). No connection with institutions or public figures was confirmed, although several connections were suspected.

• FINANCING

There is no information available to confirm that the portal was funded.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <https://zlovenija.tumblr.com/tagged/pisma>

Contact not available, organizers remained anonymous.

CROATIA

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Dosta je mržnje reporting tool

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The website Dosta je mržnje is developed as a user-friendly tool for citizens to easily report hate speech online and offline. It was created as a response to the frequent presence of hate speech in public.

This practice is an example of cooperation among organizations active in combating hate speech and strengthening freedom of expression. It offers possibilities to report content considered illegal or representing harassment, discrimination or incitement to hatred and violence.

• PERIOD

The practice is active from 2016 to present.

• ORGANIZERS

Initially, the civil society organizations Human Rights House Zagreb and Gong created the tool / website. In 2018, the Centre for Peace Studies joined in as administrator.

• FINANCING

The practice is funded through different projects of the partners and administrators, mostly by the EC's Rights, Equality and Citizenship (REC) Programme.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: www.dostajemrznje.hr

Contact: Tina Đaković, coordinator, dostajemrznje@gmail.com

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Web portal Medijska pismenost (Media Literacy)

● WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

Medijska pismenost (Media Literacy) portal primarily supports parents, guardians and teachers in raising their own media literacy level and the level of media skills and media knowledge of children. Also, the portal serves as a central place for information on media education, media literacy, and policies and trends in the media and the audio-visual industry.

The goal of the portal is to encourage discussion about the media and the safe use of technologies.

● PERIOD

The portal is active from 2015 to the present.

● ORGANIZERS

The portal was founded by the Agency for Electronic Media and UNICEF Croatia, who were later joined by various actors.

● FINANCING

The creation of the portal was a joint effort of the Agency for Electronic Media and UNICEF Croatia. Since June 2016, the portal has been completely financed through the Agency for Electronic Media, an independent regulatory body financed directly from the media industry it regulates.

● INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <http://www.medijskapismenost.net/>

Contact: medijskapismenost@e-mediji.hr

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Mobile application by the Ministry of the Interior – Security and Trust

● WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The mobile application by the Ministry of the Interior - Security and Trust - is intended for citizens to report criminal offences, misdemeanours and other events (i.e. hateful graffiti, public incitement to violence, etc.) to the police via smartphones. In addition to photos, the app has recently been improved so that citizens can also upload and send short videos. The application was created as part of the E-Police project and can be installed on all three operating systems, Android, iOS and Windows Phone OS. The recent upgrade has expanded the possibilities for citizens to report various events to the police when they may not be able to make a call for security reasons.

● PERIOD

This practice was established in 2015 and it is currently active.

● ORGANIZERS

The owner of the application is the Ministry of the Interior of the Republic of Croatia. The practice is carried out by police officers.

● FINANCING

The Security and Trust mobile application was financed from HAKOM's broadband internet development project and partly from the budget of the Ministry of the Interior (upgrade of the app).

● INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: App is available at [Google Play](#) and web site of the Ministry of the Interior,

<https://policija.gov.hr/aplikacije-za-e-dojave-sumnjivih-dogadjaja/172>

Contact: pitanja@mup.hr

¹ HAKOM - Croatian Regulatory Authority for Network Industries (Hrvatska regulatorna agencija za mrežne djelatnosti), www.hakom.hr

SERBIA

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

The “Virtual becomes reality” initiative

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

Digital violence and work on its prevention are the central themes of this initiative, launched in 2012 when the CSO Libero joined the Council of Europe’s (CoE) “No Hate Speech Movement” campaign. Since then, this organization has developed and implemented a series of non-formal educational programmes to empower and support young people to cope with the digital world’s challenges adequately.

Adults, representatives of institutions and systems that provide support to children and young people and react in the situations when intervention is necessary—teachers, social workers, young lawyers, CSO representatives, and many others—have been educated. Since 2019, an online education programme has been available.

An extensive online campaign was also conducted, aiming to inform young people about the importance of education on the topic of protection from digital violence.

• PERIOD

The initiative was launched in 2012, and some of its activities are still ongoing.

• ORGANIZERS

The holder of the initiative is the Belgrade-based youth organization Libero. The CoE, UNICEF Serbia, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Serbia, Network of Organizations for Children of Serbia, the Municipality of Vračar and CIVILNET network enabled the development and long life of the initiative with their financial, technical and professional support.

• FINANCING

The initiative was financially supported by the Ministry of Youth and Sports, UNICEF Serbia and the CoE. However, with the closing of the CoE’s campaign, the local partners’ financial support, which would have enabled the continuation of the initiative in its full scope, ceased.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <http://virtuelnopostajestvarnost.org/>

Contact: Miloš Pavlović, office@libero.org.rs

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

“Anonymous Hatred” and “H8index Database of Verbal Violence”

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

The goals and activities of the “Anonymous Hatred” project were focused in several directions. First of all, to raise the awareness of experts and the general public about the prevalence of hate speech on the internet, primarily on informative internet portals and social networks in Serbia. Noticing the public’s need to be informed and actively involved in the fight against the negative consequences of spreading extremist attitudes and ideologies, the web portal H8Index – Database of Verbal Violence was created. The cooperation with the relevant institutions responsible for the suppression of hate speech was established and an analysis of their previous practice was performed. Also, the Recommendations for the advancement of the punishment policy for hate speech, the improvement of informing the public about the prevalence of hate speech and extremism on the internet as well as means of protection against such actions were created.

• PERIOD

This project was implemented from November 2017 to October 2018.

• ORGANIZERS

The organizers were the Belgrade Center for Human Rights, in cooperation with the New Media Center LIBER, two civil society organizations that have joined their expertise in the fields of human rights and freedoms, and phenomena related to social media and digital literacy.

• FINANCING

This project was supported by the Open Society Foundation, Serbia.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <http://www.bgcentar.org.rs/>

Contact: Dušan Pokuševski, dusan@bgcentar.org.rs

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Deconstruction of Fake News (Fake News Tragač)

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

Since its founding in 1998, the Novi Sad School of Journalism (NSSJ) has promoted communication without discrimination, intolerance and hostility. In that regard, in 2017, the web portal Fake News Tragač was established. Since then, it has contributed to the fight against hate speech online by deconstructing fake and manipulative media content, and educating media workers and the public to critically analyze/read the news and check the sources.

The editorial staff of Fake News Tragač monitors the reporting of traditional and online media daily and analyzes the accuracy of published information—the authenticity of sources, presented facts, photos and videos. Posts on social networks are also analyzed, in cases when false and manipulative information is published on the official profiles of important subjects of socio-political life in Serbia which have proven to be the most common sources of false information that contain and/or provoke comments from followers with elements of hate speech.

• PERIOD

Fake News Tragač was founded in 2017, and in 2018, it was entered in the Media Register of the Business Registers Agency of Serbia.

• ORGANIZERS

NSSJ gathered a team of young educators and journalists around Fake News Tragač, and a dedicated team that manages the programme, enabling the realization of educational programmes and continuous publishing of content on the portal.

• FINANCING

The activities of Fake News Tragač are financed through various projects by the Open Society Foundation, Serbia; Netherlands' Fund for Regional Partnership – MATRA, National Endowment for Democracy – NED and Hedaya with EU financial assistance.

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information: <https://fakenews.rs/>

Contact: Stefan Janjić, stefan@fakenews.rs

TITLE OF THE GOOD PRACTICE

Campaign against hate speech on YouTube – “Clickbait” and “Drama” videos

• WHAT IS THE GOOD PRACTICE ABOUT?

Since 2017, the Deutsche Welle (DW) Academy has been implementing the project “Young Media – Media for and with young people” in Serbia and the Western Balkans region. Its activities are aimed at strengthening the capacities of the media to cover topics relevant to young people, as well as young people to critically consume media content.

Under the auspices of this project, in 2019, eight young influencers from Serbia launched a campaign against hate speech and aggression on the YouTube scene in Serbia. Two videos were recorded and published to point out the responsibility of YouTubers (already established, but also the young people who are just starting out in this “business”) for the content they publish, and to encourage public debate on ethically acceptable and unacceptable content.

• PERIOD

The implementation of the project began in 2017 and will continue until 2022.

• ORGANIZERS

DW Academy is implementing this project in cooperation with local partners—the Media Association, LokalPress, the Press Council and The National Youth Council of Serbia. The campaign against hate speech and aggression on the YouTube scene, i.e. the video clips, is a product of Serbian YouTubers - Najbolji Ortaci, Cone, Dex Lik, Dule AXE, Duxa, Jenni Martin and Kovalska.

• FINANCING

The “Young Media” project is funded by the German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development (BMZ).

• INFORMATION / CONTACT

Information:

<https://www.dw.com/en/dw-akademie-in-serbia-and-the-western-balkans/a-18497351>

<https://www.dw.com/sr/klikovi-ali-i-odgovornost/a-48346807>

Links to the campaign videos:

[Clickbait \(Klikbejt\)](#)

[Drama](#)

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BOHAVE

COUNTERING HATE SPEECH ONLINE
Summary of the selected good practices of countering
hate speech online in Slovenia, Croatia and Serbia

With the financial support of the European Union.